

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PHYTOTHERAPEUTIC DRUG KANEFRON® H (TRINEFRON)
IN THE TREATMENT OF GLOMERULONEPHRITIS REVIEW OF CLINICAL EXPERIENCE
(literature review)**

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Abstract

The article highlights the use of a combination of data of plants that are part of the drug "Trinefron", which has diuretic, anti-inflammatory, antispasmodic, antioxidant and nephroprotective effects, reducing the permeability of capillaries in the mono- or combined use of its glomerulonephritis.

Goal. To evaluate the healing properties of the components of trinefron on the human body, its role in the treatment of urinary tract infections, namely glomerulonephritis.

Materials and methods. Statistical processing of data from foreign articles about the healing effect of a combined preparation from a goldenrod, mistletoe, rosemary for glomerulonephritis in MNONO therapy and combined treatment.

The results of statistical studies revealed that the effectiveness of Kanefron H in the complex treatment of glomerulonephritis in the use of monotherapy did not affect the immunological parameters and the ratio of subpopulations CD4+/CD8+, but reduced the level of immune complexes. The assessment of the nephroprotective effects of the drug was detected, namely - normalization of diuresis and speed of glomerular filtration. According to [10], a significant decrease in leukocyturia is described, but the most positive effect is observed in the combined therapy of prednisolone with canofron. Against the background of prednisolone there is an improvement in renal function with a decrease in protein, creatinine and urea in the blood.

According to a randomized prospective study conducted by Dudar, etc., there was a lower frequency of recurrence in patients with chronic recurrent pyelonephritis and cystitis, who were prevented by this remedy within 3 months after standard therapy. The maximum effect was found in patients who received a herbal remedy together with standard therapy in the acute phase of the disease.

A similar study [4] in patients with type 2 diabetes with metabolic syndrome showed patients receiving herbal mixture for prevention for 3 months and for 6 months. The antiproteinuric effect is demonstrated in patients with microalbuminuria from low to moderately high levels.

According to a one-center cohort study, published by CEBAN, among 237 patients with ureter stones up to 0.7 cm in diameter and without lesions of the urinary tract during the first 10 days of hospitalization when using combination treatment, higher rates of excretion of the renal.

According to Gaibullaev's research (2008–2009) and Kariyev (in 2010–2011), most patients with idiopathic uncomplicated calcium-oxalate kidney stones in the fall and winter received treatment with a plant preparation on which a slight increase in diuresis. Excretion with oxalate urine (significantly), calcium (trend) and citric acid (trend) decreased, but magnesium excretion has increased (significantly) during therapy.

Conclusion.

On the basis of the above, it was found that monotherapy partially normalizes urodynamics, has an antiproteinuric effect among patients with low and moderately high microalbuminuria.

Keywords: diseases, kidneys, trinefron, disruption, healing properties, composition.

Actuality of theme. Canefron is one of the phytotherapeutic drugs, the composition of which contains goldenrod (*Centaurium erythraea*), lovistical (*Levisticum officinale*), rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) that contain phenolglycosides and phenolicarbinosides, and phenolicarbinosides, phenolglycosides, phenolglycosides, and phenolicarbinoside, phenolglycosides, and phenolicarbi-

nosides, phenolglycosides and phenolicarbinosides, phenolglycosides and phenolicarbinosides, phenolglycosides and phenolglycosides. Grass, essential oils (mistletoe, rosemary), flavonoids (golden grass, rosemary) [1,3].

It is the combination of these plants that has diuretic, anti-inflammatory, antispasmodic, antioxidant and nephroprotective effects, reducing capillary permeability. It is essential oils, phenolcarboxylic acids,

phthalides, bitterness, organic acids, vitamins, rosemary acids that have anti-inflammatory properties caused mainly by antagonism with inflammatory mediators, blocking of leukotriene synthesis. These plants increase the secretion of uric acid, promote the maintenance of urine pH in the range of 6.2 - 6.8, which is important for urate and calcium-oxalate urolithiasis. According to the study, flavonoids and rosmarinic acid can bind calcium and magnesium to chelate complexes with subsequent excretion, and the antispasmodic and diuretic action of the drug contributes to the self-release of small concretions and the rehabilitation of the urinary tract [2, 4].

Given their therapeutic effect, this combination of plants can be used in the following diseases: chronic infection of the bladder (eg, cystitis) and kidneys (eg, pyelonephritis); Non-infectious chronic inflammation of the kidneys (eg, glomerulonephritis, tubulointerstitial nephritis (Tin)).

According to the study [6,7,9], the use of this drug and the prevention of stones, or after removal of stones in the kidneys. Some authors, KG, Mills C, Bun K., mention the use of the drug during pregnancy and breastfeeding under the supervision of a doctor [5,8].

According to the evaluation [16], the use of the drug found that one tablet contains Herba Centaurii 18 mg, Radix levistici 18 mg and Folia Rosmarini 18 mg. However, when using the drug in drops, it is known that one drop contains 29 g of Herba Centaurii alcohol extract 0.6 g, Radix levistici 0.6 g and Folia rosmarini 0.6g (tincture extract) [17].

The purpose of this study. To evaluate the healing properties of the components of trinephron on the human body, its role in the prevention and treatment of urinary tract infections, namely urolithiasis, induced glomerulonephritis.

Materials and methods. Statistical processing of data from the articles of the foreign edition about the

therapeutic effect of the combined drug from the goldenrod, mistress, rosemary for glomerulonephritis in MNONO therapy and combined treatment.

Results and discussions.

According to the literature [10,16], it was found that the effectiveness of the drug in combination from the goldenrod (*Centaurium erythraea*), *LEVISTICUM officinale*, and rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) in complex treatment with glomerulonephritis.

This study [10,11] was performed on animals with glomerulonephritis. In the study revealed immunopathological changes characteristic of autoimmune pathology, namely a decrease in CD8+ T-cell, CD4+ T-helpers of blood and increase of immunoregulatory index ($p \leq 0.05$). It is known that CD4+ T cells play a crucial role in the induction of Gaiman's nephritis. According to the results of the study, the concentration of circulating immune complexes in the serum of animals increased 25 times, and the level of cryoglobulin increased 5.4 times compared to almost healthy animals

Assessing the treatment of monotherapy and combinations of prednisolone with Kanefron found that at the level of circulating immune complexes on the animal model of active autoimmune glomerulonephritis Gaiman was positive, especially with the use of combination therapy.

This indicated a decrease in proteinuria, leukocyte and hematuria, as well as a decrease in erythrocyte those waxy casts (sediment) in the urine of animals.

Against the background of the proposed treatment [10,12], total cholesterol, creatinine and urea increased significantly. In some cases, [10] the accumulation of protein products of progressive oxidation (AOPP) and carbonyl protein groups was noted in the blood, which confirmed the development of chronic renal pathology in animals.

Table 1 presents the experimental effect of this therapy [10, 13] on immunological indicators in research.

Table 1.

The effect of prednisolone therapy, trinephron and their combination on the main immunological markers of autoimmune kidney pathology (n = 8 in each group)

Group	Research parameters			
	CD3+, $\times 10^9 / \mu$	CD4 + CD3+, %	CD8 + CD3+, %	Immunoregulatory index (CD4+/CD8+)
ПЗО	6,7 ± 0,15	65,2 ± 0,9	54,1 ± 1,15	2,26 ± 0,04
AIG	6,5 ± 0,11	61,0 ± 1,6*	35,6 ± 1,5*	3,01 ± 0,07*
AIG + Prednisolone	5,9 ± 0,11 */†	62,1 ± 1,1	40,2 ± 1,5*/†	2,74 ± 0,07*/†
AIG + CAN	6,6 ± 0,11#	61,9 ± 1,2	36,2 ± 1,6*	3,00 ± 0,09*
AIG + Prednisolone + CAN	6,1 ± 0,11*/†	64,2 ± 0,7	44,5 ± 0,7*/†/#	2,58 ± 0,04*/†

* -removings are reliable relative to the PZO group, $p \leq 0.05$

† - distinct reliable relative to the AII group, $p \leq 0.05$

-distinctions are probable relative to the group of prednisolone, $p \leq 0.05$

Table 2 presents the positive dynamics of biochemical parameters in glomerulonephritis.

Table 2.

Influence of combination therapy on biochemical parameters of blood in glomerulonephritis
(average $\pm$ SEM, n = 8)

Group	Research parameters				
	BUN, mmol/l	Kreatinine, mkmol/l	Holesterole, mmol/l	AOPP, mkmol/l	PCO, nmol/mg
PZO	5,3 $\pm$ 0,2	60,4 $\pm$ 3,5	2,22 $\pm$ 0,08	68,0 $\pm$ 10,1	0,89 $\pm$ 0,12
AIG	8,3 $\pm$ 0,6*	178,4 $\pm$ 11,9*	2,69 $\pm$ 0,17*	248,1 $\pm$ 13,1*	3,94 $\pm$ 0,31*
AIG + Prednisolone	6,5 $\pm$ 0,5*/†	102,3 $\pm$ 10,8*/†	1,97 $\pm$ 0,15*/†	154,6 $\pm$ 11,0*/†	2,59 $\pm$ 0,18*/†
AIG + CAN	8,7 $\pm$ 0,8*#	122,1 $\pm$ 9,3*/†	2,39 $\pm$ 0,23*	204,0 $\pm$ 20,3*/#	3,38 $\pm$ 0,17*/#
AIG + Prednisolone + CAN	5,5 $\pm$ 0,4*/†	87,2 $\pm$ 6,1*/†	1,72 $\pm$ 0,11*/†	105,7 $\pm$ 11,98*/†/#	1,99 $\pm$ 0,11*/†/#

* -witness reliable relative to the PZO group, $p \leq 0.05$

† – -distinct are probable against AIG group, $p \leq 0.05$

-distinctions are probable against the group of prednisolone, $p \leq 0.05$

According to [14], Table 3 presents the effect of combination therapy on the state of renal function in glomerular.

Table 3

The effect of therapy on kidney function in glomerulonephritis (average $\pm$ SEM, n = 8 in each group)

Groups	research parameters		
	Diuresis, ml/day	gchof, ml/min	protein, g/mmolCr
ПЗО	13,3 $\pm$ 0,6	4,50 $\pm$ 0,32	0,13 $\pm$ 0,01
AIG	5,6 $\pm$ 0,5*	0,63 $\pm$ 0,13*	1,05 $\pm$ 0,14*
AIG + Prednisolone	10,5 $\pm$ 0,9*/†	2,98 $\pm$ 0,45*/†	0,43 $\pm$ 0,03*/†
AIG + CAN	9,7 $\pm$ 0,9*/†	1,37 $\pm$ 0,14*/†/#	0,70 $\pm$ 0,05*/#
AIG + Prednisolone + CAN	12,5 $\pm$ 1,1†	3,24 $\pm$ 0,23*/†	0,29 $\pm$ 0,05*/†

* -witness reliable relative to the PZO group, $p \leq 0.05$

† – -distinct are probable against AIG group, $p \leq 0.05$

-distinctions are probable against the group of prednisolone, $p \leq 0.05$

According to Sivak KV, Lesovskaya EE, Stoxman KI [10] Prednisolone or trinephron monotherapy is found to include various positive pharmacological effects, namely, a moderate increase in CD4+ lymphocytes to normal values, an increase in CD8+ cytotoxic lymphocytes, but incomplete normalization of CD4+/CD8+ lymphocyte. The use of prednisolone reduced the total number of lymphocytes, the concentration of immune complexes and the level of cryoglobulin. Against this background, there was a decrease in the content of urea, creatinine, general cholesterol and albumin [15].

It is known [4,6,10,13] that the use of trinephron in independent exposure does not change the immunological parameters and the ratio of subpopulations CD4+/CD8+, but only has a moderate positive effect on creatinine levels.

Data on the influence of trinephron is covered in the works by the authors of Sivak KV, Lesovskaya EE, Brenner B. [4,6,10,13], where it is found that the main

targets The drug normalized diuresis and glomerular filtration rate. However, the antioxidant effect is confirmed by the tendency to reduce PCO in the blood.

The combined treatment of prednisolone + trinephron has been repeatedly described in the works of Sivak KV, Lesovskaya EE, Brenner B., [4,6,10,13,], where the positive immunological effect was detected on cellular and humoral immunity. Due to this, proteinuria decreased, creatinine and blood urea decreased, and ggs were increased.

Complex use of glucocorticoid with phytotherapeutic drug increased CD8+ lymphocyte.

Research conducted by L.A. Sinyakova and I.V. Kosovo, were not controlled. Their study was attended by 304 patients who received a vegetable mixture as an addition to basic therapy during acute phase, or for prevention (Table 4)

According to them, it was found that the use of the drug during the first year nopathic noted recurrent phenomena.

Table 4

Number of patients, duration of herbs therapy and number of side effects
(According to the results of LA Sinyakova and IV Kosovo)

Help	Patients(n)	Duration	Side Phenomenon	Dosage
1	27	3 months	0	2 tablets or 50 drops 3 times a day
2	60	1 month	0	2 tablets or 50 drops 3 times a day
3	47	1 month	0	2 tablets three times a day
4	65	3 months	0	2 tablets or 50 drops 3 times a day
4	62	6 months	0	2 tablets or 50 drops 3 times a day
5	60	3 months	no report	2 tablets or 50 drops 3 times a day
6 + 7	110	2 months	No specific report	2 tablets 3 times a day for 4 weeks or 2 tablets or 50 drops 3 times a day for 8 weeks
8	135	1 month	0	2 tablets three times a day
9	32	2 months	0	50 drops three times a day
9	18	4 months	0	50 drops three times a day

According to the results of the study TS Perepanova and P.L. The hazan group of patients receiving this drug showed an increase in diuresis, a slight decrease in bacteriuria, frequency of periods without recurrence [16,17].

The research conducted by Dudar IO, Loboda OM, Krot VF, Khimich VI, Kryzhanivska VM, Brizachenko, showed a lower frequency of recurrence in patients with chronic recurrent pyelonephritis and cystitis received Prevention agent within 3 months after standard therapy [5].

DD Ivanov and co -authors conducted a similar study, where they demonstrated that patients with type 2 diabetes with metabolic syndrome had a positive effect that had received the remedy for 3 and 6 months. Antiproteinuric effect was also found in patients with microalbuminuria.

Conclusion.

On the basis of the above, it was found that monotherapy partially normalizes urodynamics, has an antiproteinuric effect among patients with low and moderately high microalbuminuria.

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